

Recommended citation: Neumann, A., & Bernardino, J. (2017). Ethical Dilemmas of a Software Engineer . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 870-877). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698299.

Ethical Dilemmas of a Software Engineer

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ABSTRACT

In the Information Age machines and devices are always being controlled by computers. With this, many ethical questions arise. Is a machine allowed to harm someone in favor of saving somebody else? Who is responsible for harmful actions of an autonomous car? How soft or hard should the algorithm that finds a fitting donation organ for a patient be programmed? The base of all these machines and computers is their source code, written by a human programmer. Therefore, we need to understand the ethical implications of the programmer's code. The purpose of this paper is to identify ethical implications that can result from the source-code of a program or a machine.

Conference Key Areas: Ethics in Engineering Education

Keywords: Ethics in Computing, Ethical Code, Implications of software code

1 INTRODUCTION

We live in the time of the digital revolution. We see computer-based systems wherever we go and most people cannot imagine a world without computer systems anymore. These systems are made of the actual device, known as hardware, and the source code, known as software. The software controls the hardware and makes the hardware useless without it. The base of the software is their source code, written by a human programmer, which implies that the programmer can define the possible

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actions of the hardware. The combination of software and hardware forms a usable computing system, which can range from a calculator over the airbag control unit of a car to cockpit elements of an airplane. Having this in mind, some people argue that it is the programmers fault, if the airbag did not explode during a car accident and hold the programmer responsible for the consequences. Considering the fact, that the programmer created this bug that led to the failure unintentionally, it is difficult to determine the person who is responsible for bad consequences of a software failure. The software development process involves many areas such as architecture, design, coding and testing, which results in the share of responsibility among those persons who work in one of these areas. The authors in [1] say that it is too much for a single human to be held responsible for all bad consequences in any profession. Furthermore, software systems are characterized by their complexity, which makes it difficult to predict future consequences.

This paper does not focus on the findings of the responsible person for the bad consequences of any kind of software failure, but rather focuses on the possible bad implications that can result from software failures. Besides providing an overview about general ethical coding practices that are known to help keeping bad implications to a minimum, we present more complex ethical dilemmas the software developers must face. The main contribution of this paper is to clarify ethical implications that can result from a programmer's code to alert programmers about their responsibility to keep bad consequences of their code to a minimum.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 overviews existing literature. Section 3 reviews general ethical coding practices a programmer should follow and section 4 and 5 discusses more complex software systems that require more insights to understand how the programmer should code to follow ethical guidelines. Finally, section 6 concludes this paper.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

To the best of our knowledge, there is no work that focuses on the ethical implications that can result from a programmers code to clarify the importance of software engineering ethics. Despite this, several research efforts have been carried out that focus on other aspects of computing ethics.

The authors in [1] provide an insight about the ethical responsibility of the software engineer by analyzing how far software engineers can be hold responsible for bad consequences of their software products. Because of the complexity of software systems and difficultness to predict consequences, the authors reveal it inadequate to analyze the responsibility only by the occurring consequences.

In [2], general ethics in software development are discussed, which include privacy, encryption, trust, freedom of speech and intellectual property.

Software engineering deals mainly with information, so that the main values concern truth, such as fairness and sincerity, honesty and integrity and earnestness etc., which are part of the ACM software engineering code of ethics and professional practice [3]. These guidelines also describe professional practices to avoid bad practices that could result in defective products, including appropriate testing and a good documentation. Above all these professional practices stands the public interest, which is based on health, safety and welfare.

There is several literature available that focusses on ethics in computing in general [4]–[7]. These books provide insight about ethical concerns that appear in the computation technology.

3 ETHICAL DILEMMAS OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERS

Computer programmers encounter several ethical issues [4]. In this section, we review ethical dilemmas that a programmer must face every day. We are referring to all types of software developer, which have different roles in the software development process. Most of them are programming code in various languages, but having their focus on different aspects of the end-product. A code programmer focuses on the creation of a software product, whereas the test programmer wants to guarantee the correctness and robustness of the software product. Software developer receive the information about what to code in forms of software specifications, which describe the requirements for the software product. In the following, we present scenarios of ethical issues that can occur during the software development process, which include the following ethical dilemmas:

- Coding Practices
- Code Review
- Programmers and Viruses
- Programmer Security Responsibility

For each topic, we discuss common ethical issues and present ethical guidelines that can minimize immoral consequences.

3.1 Coding Practices

Programmers face a lot of ethical dilemmas during their general coding practice. Most of them result from an incomplete communication between client and developer, short knowledge of the required programming tasks, simple boringness or laziness and most often the source, a lack of time to complete the task.

Bad code is not fulfilling all requirements of the software specifications. It can result from not realizing the complexity of the specifications and therefore underestimating the whole project. It can also result from client pressure that are in great need of satisfying deadlines. Finally, bad code can be written by programmers that do not have the technical knowledge to successfully meet the required software specifications.

Consider the following example: A software development team is in the final stage of finishing a software product, but one programmer writes bad code and slows the process down. Two other programmers want to rewrite this code without notifying management to put the project back on track. On the one hand, this covers up someone else's failings and could put future projects at risk. On the other hand, we cannot expect that everyone always succeeds and it is better for everybody to work in an environment, where everyone is supported, rather than blamed for his/her failings. To this end, supporting team members is always recommended, but instead of covering up someone else's failings, one should seek permission from the project management to support him/her and fix the code together.

Weak code results from lazy, careless or overworked programmers. Due to unrealistic deadlines, programmers can become overworked. The ethical dilemma of

doing the job versus doing the job to the best of our ability arises. Doing the job right, by investing extra hours usually pays off in the end, but could also result in the miss of a deadline. To this end, it is important to find an ethical balance between doing the best you can and doing the job just as required to satisfy any deadline.

Keeping up-to-date with the latest development practices takes a lot of time and does usually not fit in during the regular working hours. If the company does not provide extra educational seminars to provide new or upcoming technical coding practices, it is up to the programmers how to choose. Many programmers do this on the fly, because they are interested in the topic and have fun doing so. Others simply do not have the time to invest extra working hours into keeping their programming skills always up-to-date. To this end, if the job management does not provide educational seminars, it remains ethical to not acquire the latest coding practices.

3.2 Code Review

Code reviewing provides a check and balance for the created software product. A code review is performed in three different ways: by a third party, by a coworker or by an automated software. Simple code reviewing makes sure that the code has no basic vulnerabilities. More complex code reviewing is known as penetration test, which will try to penetrate the security of the program.

Doing **lazy code reviews**, because you know that everyone writes decent code could either save time or cause a lot of damage. It is important to know the priority and complexity of the project to decide how thorough the code review should be. As a programmer, you should be able to find a feeling for the needed thoroughness of the code review. If you want to make sure to not cause any damage afterwards, you should prevent lazy reviews.

There are many tools available that can do an **automated code review**. Therefore, we can ask if it is ethical to completely rely on these tools. These tools have their weaknesses and some of their code adjustments can be irrelevant and not as optimal as suggested. It is therefore important to find a balance between the tool suggestions that can be helpful for future changes and suggestions that are not relevant or even not suitable.

3.3 Programmers and Viruses

Viruses can be introduced into software development, either intentional or unintentional, which results in ethical problems. Viruses can be propagated within the development environment due to lack of attention. Programmers can be responsible for populating them in the development environment.

Is it ethical to use your **company computer at home** or at the university to continue your studies? This puts the laptop at a higher risk to contracting a virus than within the company network. Is it appropriate to put the company laptop at such a risk, or should you keep the company laptop at the workplace? Using the company laptop outside the work place is a difficult issue and the way this is handled varies from business to business. To this end, it is necessary to discuss this matter with upper management and to be on the safe side you should avoid using company resources for private affairs.

The company allowed you to take the company laptop home and you have unknowingly **contracted a virus** while studying in the university, which then infected

the whole network at work. Should you confess that you got the virus from studying in the university? Not telling how the virus was contracted will extend the process of finding and destroying the virus. This would be unethical and could cause even more damage to the corporate network than it already does. You should confess that you made a mistake and provide any details that could help eliminating the virus.

Downloading shareware involves many ethical issues. Downloading shareware can help programmers to reduce their time coding enormously. Every IT department should have strict rules concerning downloading shareware to not run into problems. Forbidding the use of shared codes will make the programmers job more difficult and subsequently less time efficient. The programmer might also lose interest, because s/he does not like programming code that is publicly available and might consider it as a waste of time. There is no standard policy available and the IT department and the programmers should find a balance for this topic.

3.4 Programmer Security Responsibility

The security of a software product involves many areas. These areas include among others security issues for API calls, temporary fixes and the use of backdoors.

If you are writing code and are using functions from other APIs, should you **assume that these APIs are already secure**? Or is it the programmer's responsibility to make sure that the API he is using is secure, by implementing security features such as error-handling routines to meet the company's security requirements? Using external APIs in your code always increases the potential security risks. The problem is that checking each external API for security vulnerabilities takes a lot of time, which is usually not available. To that end, it is up to the programmer to find a good balance between doing the job and ensuring that the product meets the required security specifications.

A **temporary fix** makes the program function correctly but it is not the optimal solution for the problem. Is it ethical to perform a temporary program fix, even though the future outcome could result in security or other problems? In the reality, temporary fixes are common practices, because companies consider it more important to meet deadlines instead of fixing every problem with the best solution. The temporary fixes are then usually improved by better solutions in future software patches or updates. As an example, Microsoft uses this technique for patches that address security weaknesses and we argue that it is a decision of upper management how to proceed with temporary fixes.

Back doors are implemented by programmers to get into the system in case something goes wrong with the application. If the program locks itself, the only way to get access to the program to free the system resources is by using a back door. Integrating back doors into a software program is a security risk. If the bad guys find out about how to access the backdoor, they can easily get access to the system. Is it ethical to implement back doors, even though you know that it would be possible to get into the system during a lockout by other means? Implementing back doors into the application involves a security risk and should be discussed with the management before implementing. Sometimes, back doors are important, because it is the only way to get into the application if a serious development problem occurs. If there are alternatives for handling those issues available, these are the better and more secure solutions.

4 CODING ETHICALLY – AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES

When programming the behavior of an autonomous car, much more difficult and complex ethical questions arise. Following precisely the ethical coding practices does not guarantee that an autonomous car will act ethically in all situations. Consider the following example: A drunken man walks along the sidewalk and falls on the street directly in front of a driverless car, which kills him instantly. The victim's family claims the vehicle manufacturer responsible for the death, because the car could have swerved around the man, crossing the double yellow line and colliding with an empty driverless car. A reconstruction of the accident by collecting the car sensors information confirms this. The vehicle manufacturer asks the chief software designer: "Why didn't the car swerve?".

If a person would have been controlling the vehicle, s/he would not be blamed for not making the right decision. A court would never ask this person, why s/he did not act the right way in this critical moment. The person could have panicked and acted on instinct and s/he would not be considered as responsible for the drunken man's dead. When robots or machines are driving, this is a whole different story and the question, why the machine did not find the best outcome for the situation becomes valid.

While human drivers can decide how to crash in real time, an automated vehicle's decision of how to crash was defined by a programmer a priori. The vehicle interprets the sensor data to decide how to react, but the logic of this decision has been implemented ahead of time. On the one hand, this works well if a crash can be avoided. On the other hand, if a crash cannot be avoided and people will get injured, the vehicle must decide what is the best way to crash. Consequently, this becomes an ethical decision. As an example, the programmer must decide whether the car prefers a severe one-vehicle crash over a moderate two-vehicle crash or chooses another way that has a low probability for not crashing at all, but a high probability for a severe two-vehicle crash, as shown in Figure 1 below [8].

Fig. 1. Diagram of three alternative ways to crash for an autonomous vehicle when an oncoming bus suddenly enters the vehicle's lane

This ethical problem refers to the moral experiment of the Trolley Problem, in which it is to decide whether to let five persons being killed and leave one person unharmed or to rescue five persons by actively killing one person [9]. This dilemma has been often discussed in literature and has not provided a solution and that is why there is no obvious way to effectively encode human morality in the software of autonomous vehicles [8].

A different approach to deal with this problem was provided in [10], by introducing risk management as an alternative way. Autonomous vehicles must constantly save the values of dangerous situations to compare with different objects on the road during crashes. How these values are formulated and the risks of driving are shared to other automated cars include ethical elements. Risk management techniques can be used to evaluate these possible risks. Using these techniques, it seems manageable to design ethical autonomous cars. Because these solutions might not be perfect, it is important to justify them by widely accepted ethical principles.

With the rising of autonomous cars, manufacturers and software developers will have to defend the actions of their autonomous cars in ways that are much more difficult to explain than what the normal driver would have to. The developers should therefore learn from experiences in similar areas such as industrial safety standards [11] and should continue to study the ethical implications of automated vehicles. We aimed to provide insight into the possible bad implications of autonomous vehicles that are very complex and not yet completely possible to prevent.

5 CODING ETHICALLY – HEALTH CARE ORGAN DONATION

The most difficult problem for an organ transplantation is the unavailability of a suitable donor organ. The next difficulty is the finding of a suitable donor organ at the right time. Programmers have designed algorithms for finding suitable donor organs. This is a hard combinatorial optimization problem and involves a lot of information, such as blood type, antibody information of the patient and antigen information of the donor [12]. Programming such an algorithm that involves life and death decisions implies critical and ethical decisions for the programmer. They face questions like how soft or hard should the matching algorithm be, or should younger and healthier patients be preferred over older, more unhealthy patients. Other questions concern, if the healthy-living patients should be privileged over patients that heavily drink or smoke. There are different ethical models available and in practical use that use different principles to judge which people for an organ transplantation or vaccines during a pandemic influenza get priority rights. These principles include *First-come, first-served*; *Sickest first*; *Prognosis* and other *instrumental values*.

In [13], the authors evaluated eight ethical principles for rare medical interventions. They state that no single principle can consider all ethical elements and it is therefore necessary to combine different principles into a multi-principle system. They quantified three existing and practical systems and provided a new system that prioritizes younger people, incorporates the medical prognosis and adapts the principles *save the most lives*; *random lottery selection*; *instrumental values*. For applying an ethical system like this in practice, these ethical values also need to be integrated into the algorithm by a programmer, because the selection of which person will receive the next available suitable organ will be processed by a computer.

When a software developer has the task of programming parts of such an algorithm s/he does not have to create these different ethical principles into the code by himself. The required specifications will already imply these ethical principles and the way they should be implemented. It is still important that the developers know what implications their code might have. It is a big difference if the programmer is coding the specifications for a website or for an organ donation algorithm.

For all kinds of software that is directly used to ensure the health of humans, the ethical implications that can result from software failures can be vast. Of course, it is not only the programmers task to ensure the correctness of his code in such cases.

There are other professions like quality and risk management that will thoroughly review and test the software to avoid any failures, but it is also the programmers task to understand the possible implications of his code. When programming a heart-beat control monitor the programmer should ensure that s/he is following ethical coding practices to reduce the possibility of future serious consequences for patients [14].

6 CONCLUSION

In this work, we reviewed best practices for ethical coding issues that face software engineers every day. We also provided a brief insight on other software programming topics, autonomous vehicles and organ donation, which can have very diverse and complex ethical implications. Every software program that involves humans or the environment as a user or as a part, can have ethical implications.

With this being said, we argue that it is important to teach software engineering ethics education, to teach students how to code ethically and demonstrate the possible implications of their computer programs. It is from utmost importance for every software developer to think about possible bad implications of their code. Having possible ethical implications of the developed program in mind, the developer will try to avoid them, which will result in a better software product.

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